

**THE ISSUE OF E- LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES
IN A MODERN EDUCATION.**

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Abstract. *Language students have a fantastic opportunity to get training in a flexible setting through e- learning. For students who are under pressure to manage their professional and/or personal duties, this form of education offers a flexible time management system. Research on remote language learning has primarily concentrated on how new technologies can impact distance education due to the development of new technical advancements. Monitoring the shift in focus in research on remote language learning is equally crucial. Investigating significant potential research areas, recognising present approaches, identifying potential gaps in prior efforts, and providing solutions to overcome limitations in this subject are therefore of utmost relevance. This article is devoted to examining problems with contemporary distant learning. This article's primary goal is to provide evidence for distant learning as an innovative form of instruction. This study illustrates how to acquire four skills—listening, writing, speaking, and reading—at a distance. It provides illustrations of simple ways to use electronic resources (textbooks, dictionaries, and electronic books).*

Keywords: *e-learning, distance learning , modern education, problems, solutions, electronic materials.*

Introduction

The discipline of education was impacted by the rapid renewal of technologies and knowledge in many areas of human endeavor. The demands of a person seeking educational services can no longer be met by traditional types of education. Teachers from all over the world turned to information technology for assistance in solving this issue and started using it actively in distant learning for their educational activities. Distance learning is education that takes place while a student and teacher are separated by physical distance. [1]

Methods and results

Speaking, listening, reading, and writing are the primary modes of action taught while teaching a foreign language, not the scientific principles. Foreign languages that are unusual must be organized for distant learning so that students can complete their assignments independently while still participating in the tutor's prescribed activities. Think about the opportunities for distance learning in various contexts: Reading. Each student who is learning to read remotely must have access to a device that allows them to read and practice this skill.

The principles for reading letters and letter combinations, as well as exercises on how to apply them when reading specific words and sentences, must be included in a study guide, whether it be printed or digital. There are already programs able to determine the correctness of the words read by ear.

In virtual communication, being intercultural by the character, the lecturer or professor should certainly take into account the specificity of linguistic means and resources, the rules of interaction, because of technological features that can not only contribute to the dialogue, but also complicate collaboration and understanding. The teacher or the lecturer faces both methodological and didactic tasks aimed at optimizing the communication process, which is determined by the

ability to dialogue with the interlocutors, to formulate their thoughts, define the tasks, avoid the ambiguity of the messages, etc.

Moreover, in reviewing of the results of electronic dictionaries implementation in the learning process it was found that students prefer to use handheld electronic dictionaries in the classroom. For the translation of the original texts on economics they use printed dictionaries or computer translator. The quality of such work is low and does not meet the required standards of translation. To increase interest in electronic dictionaries, it is necessary to develop a set of specific exercises that facilitate the acquisition of skills of using a dictionary.

The interest of teachers in higher education to new learning tools allows to see the educational opportunities of modern hardware and software in teaching a foreign language. The use of modern information technology can improve students' motivation to learn, their responsibility, the level of self-actualization, and form communication skills and intercultural competence. It can motivate stronger students to help others and strengthen the interaction between students. It can also give students a platform to discuss topics covered in class outside of university.

Discussion

Options for regulating the level of understanding should be considered if the goal of training is to educate comprehension skills when reading foreign language literature. It may involve quizzes, questions and answers, retellings, and a variety of other tasks. In order to read for distance learning, a student must follow the instructions laid out by the teacher in advance, keep a journal in which they should reflect on their work with the text, jot down questions that they should then ask the teacher, respond to the questions in the manual, and carry out control tasks. Using network and case technology, one can study literature in foreign languages remotely. Teleconferences can also be used for student or teacher communication or for better teacher-student communication.

Listening.

Recently, video records have been utilized to teach listening skills with audio tools. These videos contain extralinguistic and contextual cues for interpreting mania as well as crucial visual cues. The student can process a range of sounds and visuals by pausing the stream and rewinding or pausing the video in order to better understand the auditory material. In a distant learning system, the computer and its multimedia tools are crucial to the process of learning to grasp a foreign language by ear.

Training

In the distant learning system, learning a foreign language by ear necessitates the use of pricey tools such good video cards, cameras, microphones, etc. Teaching audio-visual, however, produces good outcomes when all of this is present along with the appropriate methodological and didactic assistance.

Speaking and writing.

Communication between the student, the group, and the teacher helps students learn to talk and write (it should be highlighted that written speech is the same as oral speech, just set out on paper or electronic medium). Email, chats, and synchronous communication naming can all be used to carry out education written speech. Only teleconferences can be used for the remote learning system's teaching of stable speech.

In the process of communication, students use all types of activities:

- understanding of a foreign language text and writing skills (communication through written speech);

- listening and speaking skills (communication through oral speech).

No activity can be taught without paying attention to the three aspects of learning foreign language:

Vocabulary.

Learning vocabulary occurs with the help of a textbook (or its electronic version ta), electronic applications to it, developed exercises and tasks for self-control and control troll. The whole process is supervised by a tutor. Suitable for teaching this aspect of a foreign language case technology and network technology.

Grammar. It is essential to give students access to a variety of dictionaries, textbooks, grammar reference books, as well as to regularly refresh a variety of sources of didactic linguistic knowledge, when teaching grammar. Case studies will be helpful in this situation. network technology and technology. Make use of all available channels of communication between students and teachers to discuss the application of a grammatical phenomenon.

Phonetics.

The levels of phonetics training are theoretical and practical. Brief theoretical information can be found in the theoretical stage. Practice your speech patterns, intonation, and pace throughout this period. Numerous new technologies have recently emerged that make it possible to teach phonetics through the remote education system. It should be understood, nonetheless, that teaching practical phonetics will be most effective when the student is speaking directly to the teacher, who may correct their pronunciation as he hears them. Online audio or teleconferences are the topic here.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that distance learning foreign languages can compete with traditional forms of education with the competent development of didactic and technical ron, with consistent and professional support waiting for trainees throughout the course, with high motivation of students, and the presence of all necessary technical means of teaching and electronic educational resources.

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